

On the Occasion of Approaching Fifty Years of Type II Superlattices: A Clarifying Comment

G. A. Sai-Halasz

The fifty years are counted from the appearance of our paper¹, “A New Semiconductor Superlattice” (hereafter “*the paper*”), although the term “Type II” was coined only a year later in reporting² the optical absorption properties of this new superlattice.

The purpose of the present communication is to create a permanent record of a much earlier clarification of *the paper* (see Fig. 1). *The paper* was necessarily terse because of the journal’s length restrictions. A very careful reading would have been required to follow all details. Consequently, over the years questions arose concerning the meaning of the u and u' terms in Eq. (3) of *the paper*. The substance of the response is reproduced in Fig. 1. This note was written in late 1978 or early 1979 and was mailed to anyone who inquired (electronic mail was still years away). Despite this, a consensus developed that the formalism involved additional or unspecified Bloch functions in order to calculate the properties of the new superlattice^{3,4}.

The overall approach of *the paper* was a one-dimensional Kronig–Penney framework used to obtain the superlattice envelope wave functions. In the textbook Kronig–Penney model the repeating period consists of two regions: one free-space-like and the other a potential barrier. This description was highly successful, for example, in the original GaAs–GaAlAs superlattice⁵. In contrast, we treated both layers of the superlattice period as semiconductors described within Kane’s two-band framework^{6,7}. This was stated explicitly in *the paper* immediately after Eqs. (1a–1c), and Kane’s work appeared as Ref. [15] therein.

The first line following Eq. (3) of *the paper* specifies that the u and u' functions are evaluated at given points, namely at the layer boundaries. Since the u functions are periodic, their values are identical at equivalent boundaries, including the origin. The u'/u terms enter Eq. (3) through the boundary-matching conditions of the Kronig–Penney formulation, in the same manner as the wave vectors k . Their detailed form is not arbitrary; it is restricted by Kane’s two-band model (see Fig. 1). No additional Bloch functions were introduced. The Bloch basis was fixed; only material parameters entering the Hamiltonian differed between layers.

This scheme produced quantitatively accurate results. The agreement with the experimental optical absorption edges² was particularly clear. Those measurements demonstrated that in Type II superlattices the absorption edge can be widely tuned by composition and structure, and that it may lie below the band gap of either constituent material. The two-band treatment also proved adequate in later interpretations of other Type II properties reported by the

“Esaki group” in the late 1970s and early 1980s. In addition, there was good agreement with a fundamentally different theoretical treatment of the Type II system based on the LCAO approach⁸.

It was always understood that the two-band framework describes conduction electrons and light holes. Heavy holes were treated separately within the standard Kronig–Penney formalism.

To obtain actual results for band structure, wave functions, dispersion relations, and optical properties required numerical methods. As an example, Appendix A reproduces a FORTRAN program that calculated the band structure and corresponding envelope wave functions for a Type II superlattice. This and similar programs used at the time were never intended for public distribution. The code is not optimized, lacks documentation, and reflects programming practices of that era. It is included strictly for archival purposes. The program has not been run or maintained since the late 1970s.

¹G. A. Sai-Halasz, R. Tsu, and L. Esaki, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 30, 651 (1977).

²G. A. Sai-Halasz, L. L. Chang, J.-M. Welter, C.-A. Chang, and L. Esaki, *Solid State Commun.* 27, 935 (1978).

³G. Bastard, *Phys. Rev.* B24, 5693 (1981).

⁴D. L. Smith and C. Mailhot, *Journal of Appl. Phys.*, 62, 2545 (1987).

⁵L. Esaki and R. Tsu, *IBM J. Res. Dev.* 14, 61 (1970).

⁶E. O. Kane, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1, 249 (1957).

⁷E. O. Kane, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* 12, 181 (1959).

⁸G. A. Sai-Halasz, L. Esaki, and W. A. Harrison, *Phys. Rev.* B18, 2812 (1978).

In our 77, Apl. Phys. Lett. 30, 651, publication, the u'/u terms in the equation for superlattice (SL) bands are evaluated at a given point, namely at the interface. Thus, their analytical form is: (number) \times (energy dependent term). In the kp -perturbation the energy dependent term is given independently of spacial variation; one does not have the freedom to chose it. In a two-band model the u -s are:

$$u_c = |c\rangle + b|v\rangle \quad \text{above midgap}$$

$$u_v = b|c\rangle - |v\rangle \quad \text{below midgap}$$

where b is the band mixing parameter and contains all the energy dependence. (It has combinations of terms like $(E-E_g)^{1/2}$. See Kane's papers.) The u'/u -s are in the SL expression become (number) $\times b$ or (number)/ b depending on which side are we of midgap. The number will turn out to be of the order of $2\pi/(\text{lattice constant})$. $|c\rangle$ and $|v\rangle$ are the spacial variations at the cond./val. band edges. They are orthogonal and their momentum matrix element is:

$$\langle c|p|v\rangle = \frac{m_1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{E_g}{m_r}}$$

Within these constrains imposed by the two-band model, for any Fourier series expression of $|c\rangle$ and $|v\rangle$ the superlattice band structure does not change more than $\sim 10\%$. This is in line with expectations from an the inherently simple 1D treatment. Mathematically, the independence of the SL band structure from the specific forms of $|c\rangle$ and $|v\rangle$, is the result of the Kronig-Penney type of form the u'/u -s are imbedded in. In a deeper sense it expresses that only the envelope wavefunctions are important in determining the superlattice bands. Thus, 1D two-band model captures the essential features superlattices be it of Type I or II.

Specifically, in our calculations we used (within a normalization factor that drops out) the following functions:

$$|c\rangle = \cos \frac{2\pi}{a_0} x + C \cos \frac{4\pi}{a_0} x; \quad (a_0 \text{ being the lattice constant})$$

and the same form for $|v\rangle$ with \sin . C was adjusted for each material to give the proper effective-mass lattice-constant connection from the $\langle c|p|v\rangle$ term. As it turns out, C for most III-V is only around 0.1-0.2.

We did not go into these details in the article because it seemed to us that for theoreticians these are too obvious considerations, and experimentalist wouldn't care. We clearly missed on the first part of our assumption. Since there were many inquiries about these "mysterious" u -s, I tried to say something on this subject in a talk at the 78 Semicon. Conf. in Edinburgh. (See the conference proceedings.) Of course, nobody noticed this.

George Sai-Halasz

Fig. 1. Original clarification note (late 1978 or early 1979).

UO1=DSQRT((1.D0-PIU1)/(2.D0+PIU1))	ALL25110
61 PIU2=SA2/SU2	ALL25120
IF (PIU2 .LT. 1.D0) GO TO 62	ALL25130
LS2=1	ALL25140
UO2=DSQRT((PIU2-1.D0)/(2.D0-PIU2))	ALL25150
GO TO 63	ALL25160
62 LS2=1-2	ALL25170
UO2=DSQRT((1.D0-PIU2)/(2.D0+PIU2))	ALL25180
63 AMM1=EMR1	ALL25190
AMM2=EMR2	ALL25200
DO 10 L=1, M	ALL25210
X=WF+L*HMU+2.01E-3	ALL25220
CALL MENTO(X,Y)	ALL25230
IF (L .NE. 1) GO TO 17	ALL25240
YMM=Y	ALL25250
17 CONTINUE	ALL25260
IF (Y .GT. 1.) GO TO 12	ALL25270
IF (Y .LT. 1.-2.) GO TO 13	ALL25280
10 CONTINUE	ALL25290
12 IF (L .NE. 1) GO TO 15	ALL25300
I=1	ALL25310
II=1	ALL25320
NW=1	ALL25330
N=1	ALL25340
GO TO 14	ALL25350
15 I=1-2	ALL25360
II=1-2	ALL25370
N=2	ALL25380
E(1)=WF+HMU	ALL25390
NW=4	ALL25400
GO TO 14	ALL25410
13 IF (L .NE. 1) GO TO 16	ALL25420
I=1-2	ALL25430
II=1	ALL25440
NW=3	ALL25450
N=1	ALL25460
GO TO 14	ALL25470
16 I=1	ALL25480
II=1-2	ALL25490
N=2	ALL25500
E(1)=WF+HMU	ALL25510
NW=2	ALL25520
14 CONTINUE	ALL25530
Y=YMM	ALL25540
21 CONTINUE	ALL25550
DO 1 L=1, M	ALL25560
X=WF+L*HMU+2.01E-3	ALL25570
Y1=Y	ALL25580
CALL MENTO(X,Y)	ALL25590
D1=DABS(Y1-Y)	ALL25600
25 FORMAT(2E15.6)	ALL25610
2 CONTINUE	ALL25620
IF (I .EQ. 1) GO TO 3	ALL25630
IF (Y .LT. I*II) GO TO 1	ALL25640
GO TO 4	ALL25650
3 IF (Y .GT. I*II) GO TO 1	ALL25660
4 CALL SITER(X,D1,I,II,ENER)	ALL25670
E(N)=ENER	ALL25680
N=N+1	ALL25690
NW=NW+1	ALL25700
II=(-1)**(NW-1)	ALL25710
IF (NW-4*((NW-1)/4) .LE. 2) GO TO 5	ALL25720
I=(-1)	ALL25730
GO TO 2	ALL25740
5 I=1	ALL25750
26 FORMAT(2I6)	ALL25760
GO TO 2	ALL25770
1 CONTINUE	ALL25780

19	CONTINUE	ALL25790
	N=N-1	ALL25800
	IF (N .EQ. 1) GO TO 18	ALL25810
	IF (2*(N/2) .NE. N) GO TO 6	ALL25820
	LL=0	ALL25830
	KK=N/2	ALL25840
8	DO 7 NN=1, KK	ALL25850
	N1=2*NN	ALL25860
	OBW1=E(N1)-E(N1-1)	ALL25870
	EPI=E(N1-1)+ES	ALL25880
7	PRINT 101, EPI, OBW1	ALL25890
101	FORMAT (' ', 6X, 2(F9.6, 3X))	ALL25900
	IF (LL .EQ. 0) GO TO 9	ALL25910
	EPI=E(N1+1)+ES	ALL25920
	PRINT 101, EPI	ALL25930
	GO TO 9	ALL25940
6	KK=(N-1)/2	ALL25950
	LL=1	ALL25960
	GO TO 8	ALL25970
18	EPI=E(1)+ES	ALL25980
	PRINT 101, EPI	ALL25990
9	CONTINUE	ALL26000
	IL=2*ZOLCS-1	ALL26010
	X=E(IL)+(E(IL+1)-E(IL))*XIDO	ALL26020
	CALL MENTO(X, Y)	ALL26030
	WWKD=DARCOS(Y)	ALL26040
	AU(1,1)=(1.D0,0.D0)	ALL26050
	AU(1,2)=(0.D0,0.D0)	ALL26060
	AU(2,1)=(0.D0,0.D0)	ALL26070
	AU(2,2)=(1.D0,0.D0)	ALL26080
	CALL MUNTO(X, AB1, AB2, CK1, CK2, CT1, CT2, B1F, B1D, B2F, B2D, IMM1, IMM2)	ALL26090
	CALL SMAT(AU, CIK, B1F, B1D, B2F, B2D, CK1, CK2, CT2, IMM1, IMM2)	ALL26100
	DO 44 JJ=1, 2	ALL26110
	DO 44 JI=1, 2	ALL26120
44	AU(JJ, JI)=CIK(JJ, JI)	ALL26130
	CALL SMAT(AU, CIK, B2F, B2D, B1F, B1D, CK2, CK1, CT1, IMM2, IMM1)	ALL26140
	A1A=AON	ALL26150
	BB1=CIK(2,1)/(CDEXP(API*WWKD)-CIK(2,2))	ALL26160
	BOB11=(CDEXP(API*WWKD)-CIK(1,1))/CIK(1,2)	ALL26170
	C1C=AU(1,1)+AU(1,2)*BB1	ALL26180
	CC1C=AU(2,1)+AU(2,2)*BB1	ALL26190
72	CA1A=DCONJG(A1A)	ALL26200
	CBB1=DCONJG(BB1)	ALL26210
	C1CC=DCONJG(C1C)	ALL26220
	CCC1C=DCONJG(CC1C)	ALL26230
	IF (AIMAG(CK1) .GT. 1.E-10) GO TO 73	ALL26240
	FXNOR=WW*(CDABS(A1A)**2+CDABS(BB1)**2)-	ALL26250
	1(AIMAG(A1A*CBB1)*(CDCOS(2.*WW*CK1)-1.))-REAL(A1A*CBB1)*	ALL26260
	2CDSIN(2.*WW*CK1))/CK1	ALL26270
	GO TO 74	ALL26280
73	FXNOR=2.*WW*REAL(A1A*CBB1)+API*(CDABS(A1A)**2*	ALL26290
	1(CDEXP(ANO*2.*WW*API*CK1)-1.))+CDABS(BB1)**2*	ALL26300
	2(1.-CDEXP(API*2*CK1*WW)))/(2.*CK1)	ALL26310
74	IF (AIMAG(CK2) .GT. 1.E-10) GO TO 75	ALL26320
	SXNOR=OBW*(CDABS(C1C)**2+CDABS(CC1C)**2)-	ALL26330
	1(AIMAG(C1C*CCC1C)*(CDCOS(2.*OBW*CK2)-1.))-REAL(C1C*CCC1C)*	ALL26340
	2CDSIN(2.*OBW*CK2))/CK2	ALL26350
	GO TO 76	ALL26360
75	SXNOR=2.*OBW*REAL(C1C*CCC1C)+API*(CDABS(C1C)**2*	ALL26370
	1(CDEXP(ANO*2.*OBW*API*CK2)-1.))+CDABS(CC1C)**2*	ALL26380
	2(1.-CDEXP(API*2*CK2*OBW)))/(2.*CK2)	ALL26390
76	XNOR=FXNOR+SXNOR	ALL26400
	ACDE=CDEXP(API*CK2*OBW)	ALL26410
	CATB=C1C/ACDE	ALL26420
	CDATB=CC1C*ACDE	ALL26430
	AFDIF=A1A+BB1-CATB-CDATB	ALL26440
	CFAC=API*CK2*B2F+B2D	ALL26450
	BDR1=C11*CFAC/ACDE-CC1*IMM2*ACDE*CFAC	ALL26460

	AOLIU=API*CK1*B1F+B1D	ALL26470
	BDLE=A11*AOLIU-B11*IMM1*AOLIU	ALL26480
	ADDIF=BDRI-BDLE	ALL26490
	IF (IPPI .EQ. 0) GO TO 51	ALL26500
45	DO 42 KK=1,200	ALL26510
	TT=((KK-1) * (WW+OBW) + .0011) / 200.	ALL26520
	XPHO=ELOP(TT) * (WW+OBW) / XNOR	ALL26530
C	IF (TT .GT. WW) GO TO 46	ALL26540
	TT=TT / (WW+OBW)	ALL26550
C	TT=TT/SA1	ALL26560
C	GO TO 47	ALL26570
C	46 TT=(TT-WW) / SA2+WW/SA1	ALL26580
	47 WRITE(3,107) TT	ALL26590
	42 WRITE(2,107) XPHO	ALL26600
	IF (IPPI .EQ. 1) GO TO 41	ALL26610
51	SUPE=0.	ALL26620
	TATO=0.	ALL26630
	DO 52 N=1,4	ALL26640
	SOTO=SUPE	ALL26650
	SUPE=N*WW/4.	ALL26660
	CALL QGF(ELOP, SOTO, SUPE, 48, TATI, IER)	ALL26670
52	TATO=TATO+TATI	ALL26680
	TATA=0.	ALL26690
	DO 53 N=1,4	ALL26700
	SOTO=SUPE	ALL26710
	SUPE=N*OBW/4.+WW	ALL26720
	CALL QGF(ELOP, SOTO, SUPE, 48, TATI, IER)	ALL26730
53	TATA=TATA+TATI	ALL26740
	TATO=TATO/XNOR	ALL26750
	TATA=TATA/XNOR	ALL26760
	FIN=TATO / (TATO+TATA)	ALL26770
	FUN=TATA / (TATO+TATA)	ALL26780
	PRINT 107, FIN, FUN, XNOR, TATO, TATA	ALL26790
107	FORMAT(F15.6)	ALL26800
41	STOP	ALL26810
	END	ALL26820
	SUBROUTINE KGET (EV, EG, EMR, WS, IK)	ALL26830
	IMPLICIT REAL*8 (A-H, O-Z)	ALL26840
	IK=1	ALL26850
	ZIO=2.D0*EV-EG+EG / (2.D0*EMR)	ALL26860
	ZIZ=EV**2-EV*EG	ALL26870
	TEL=ZIO**2-4.D0*ZIZ	ALL26880
	IF (TEL .LT. 0.D0) GO TO 1	ALL26890
	WS=.1312D0*(ZIO-DSQRT(TEL))	ALL26900
	IF (EV .GE. EG*(1.D0-EMR) / 2.D0) GO TO 2	ALL26910
	IK=1-2	ALL26920
	GO TO 2	ALL26930
1	PRINT 100	ALL26940
100	FORMAT(' VALENCE BAND DOES NOT EXIST IN SOME ENERGY REGION')	ALL26950
2	RETURN	ALL26960
	END	ALL26970
	SUBROUTINE SITER (OO, D1, I, II, ENER)	ALL26980
	IMPLICIT REAL*8 (D-H, O-Z)	ALL26990
	IMPLICIT COMPLEX*16 (A-C)	ALL27000
	DOUBLE PRECISION REAL	ALL27010
	COMMON /COK/ LS1, LS2, V, WW, OBW, EG1, EG2, EMR1, EMR2, HMU, UO1, UO2,	ALL27020
	1SA1, SA2, AEG1, AEG2, AMM1, AMM2, A2P, AON, ANO, API	ALL27030
	SIP=OO	ALL27040
	DO 1 K=1,100	ALL27050
	CALL MENTO(SIP, Y)	ALL27060
	YYD=Y-I*II	ALL27070
	ENER=SIP	ALL27080
	IF (DABS(YYD) .LT. D1*1.D-7/HMU) GO TO 2	ALL27090
	SIP=SIP+I*YYD*HMU/D1	ALL27100
101	FORMAT (' ', 3(E12.6, 5X))	ALL27110
1	CONTINUE	ALL27120
	ENER=0.	ALL27130
2	RETURN	ALL27140

END	ALL27150
SUBROUTINE MENTO (X,Y)	ALL27160
IMPLICIT REAL*8 (D-H,O-Z)	ALL27170
IMPLICIT COMPLEX*16 (A-C)	ALL27180
COMMON /COK/ LS1,LS2,V,WW,OBW, EG1,EG2,EMR1,EMR2,HMU,UO1,UO2,	ALL27190
1SA1,SA2,AEG1,AEG2,AMM1,AMM2,A2P,AON,ANO,API	ALL27200
X1=X	ALL27210
CALL KGET (X1,EG1,EMR1,W1S,IM1)	ALL27220
ASO=W1S	ALL27230
CK1=CDSQRT (ASO)	ALL27240
CT1=WW*CK1	ALL27250
X2=X-EG1-V+EG2	ALL27260
CALL KGET (X2,EG2,EMR2,WS2,IM2)	ALL27270
ASE=WS2	ALL27280
CK2=CDSQRT (ASE)	ALL27290
CT2=OBW*CK2	ALL27300
AA1=CK1/CDSQRT (.1312D0*AEG1*AMM1)	ALL27310
AA2=CK2/CDSQRT (.1312D0*AEG2*AMM2)	ALL27320
AB1=API*AA1/(1.D0+CDSQRT (1.D0+AA1**2))	ALL27330
AB2=API*AA2/(1.D0+CDSQRT (1.D0+AA2**2))	ALL27340
IF (IM1 .LT. 0) GO TO 31	ALL27350
B1F=AON+LS1*UO1	ALL27360
B1D=A2P*AB1*(AON+2.D0*UO1)/SA1	ALL27370
GO TO 32	ALL27380
31 B1F=AB1*(ANO-LS1*UO1)	ALL27390
B1D=A2P*(ANO-2.D0*UO1)/SA1	ALL27400
32 IF (IM2 .LT. 0) GO TO 33	ALL27410
B2F=AON+LS2*UO2	ALL27420
B2D=A2P*AB2*(AON+2.D0*UO2)/SA2	ALL27430
GO TO 38	ALL27440
33 B2F=AB2*(ANO-LS2*UO2)	ALL27450
B2D=A2P*(ANO-2.D0*UO2)/SA2	ALL27460
38 CONTINUE	ALL27470
CRFT=API*CK1+B1D/B1F	ALL27480
CRST=API*CK2+B2D/B2F	ALL27490
BNT=.5*(CRFT/CRST+CRST/CRFT)	ALL27500
BNS=CDCOS (CT1)*CDCOS (CT2)-BNT*CDSIN (CT1)*CDSIN (CT2)	ALL27510
Y=REAL (BNS)	ALL27520
1 RETURN	ALL27530
END	ALL27540
SUBROUTINE MUNTO (X,AB1,AB2,CK1,CK2,CT1,	ALL27550
1CT2,B1F,B1D,B2F,B2D,IMM1,IMM2)	ALL27560
IMPLICIT REAL*8 (D-H,O-Z)	ALL27570
IMPLICIT COMPLEX*16 (A-C)	ALL27580
COMMON /COK/ LS1,LS2,V,WW,OBW, EG1,EG2,EMR1,EMR2,HMU,UO1,UO2,	ALL27590
1SA1,SA2,AEG1,AEG2,AMM1,AMM2,A2P,AON,ANO,API	ALL27600
X1=X	ALL27610
CALL KGET (X1,EG1,EMR1,W1S,IM1)	ALL27620
ASO=W1S	ALL27630
IMM1=IM1	ALL27640
CK1=CDSQRT (ASO)	ALL27650
CT1=WW*CK1	ALL27660
X2=X-EG1-V+EG2	ALL27670
CALL KGET (X2,EG2,EMR2,WS2,IM2)	ALL27680
ASE=WS2	ALL27690
CK2=CDSQRT (ASE)	ALL27700
IMM2=IM2	ALL27710
CT2=OBW*CK2	ALL27720
AA1=CK1/CDSQRT (.1312D0*AEG1*AMM1)	ALL27730
AA2=CK2/CDSQRT (.1312D0*AEG2*AMM2)	ALL27740
AB1=API*AA1/(1.D0+CDSQRT (1.D0+AA1**2))	ALL27750
AB2=API*AA2/(1.D0+CDSQRT (1.D0+AA2**2))	ALL27760
IF (IM1 .LT. 0) GO TO 31	ALL27770
B1F=AON+LS1*UO1	ALL27780
B1D=A2P*AB1*(AON+2.D0*UO1)/SA1	ALL27790
GO TO 32	ALL27800
31 B1F=AB1*(ANO-LS1*UO1)	ALL27810
B1D=A2P*(ANO-2.D0*UO1)/SA1	ALL27820

32	IF (IM2 .LT. 0) GO TO 33	ALL27830
	B2F=AON+LS2*UO2	ALL27840
	B2D=A2P*AB2*(AON+2.D0*UO2)/SA2	ALL27850
	GO TO 38	ALL27860
33	B2F=AB2*(ANO-LS2*UO2)	ALL27870
	B2D=A2P*(ANO-2.D0*UO2)/SA2	ALL27880
38	CONTINUE	ALL27890
1	RETURN	ALL27900
	END	ALL27910
	FUNCTION ELOP(TT)	ALL27920
	IMPLICIT REAL*8 (D-H,O-Z)	ALL27930
	IMPLICIT COMPLEX*16 (A-C)	ALL27940
	COMMON /COK/ LS1,LS2,V,WW,OBW, EG1,EG2,EMR1,EMR2,HMU,UO1,UO2,	ALL27950
1	SA1,SA2,AEG1,AEG2,AMM1,AMM2,A2P,AON,ANO,API	ALL27960
	COMMON/BUS/ B1L,B2L,A11,B11,C11,CC1,CK1,CK2,IMM1,IMM2	ALL27970
	IF (TT .GT. WW) GO TO 1	ALL27980
	TRT=TT-WW	ALL27990
	A1=A11	ALL28000
	A2=B11	ALL28010
	LS=LS1	ALL28020
	CK=CK1	ALL28030
	SA=SA1	ALL28040
	BR=B1L	ALL28050
	UO=UO1	ALL28060
	IF (IMM1 .LT. 0) GO TO 11	ALL28070
	GO TO 12	ALL28080
1	TRT=TT-WW-OBW	ALL28090
	BR=B2L	ALL28100
	CK=CK2	ALL28110
	A1=C11	ALL28120
	A2=CC1	ALL28130
	UO=UO2	ALL28140
	LS=LS2	ALL28150
	SA=SA2	ALL28160
	IF (IMM2 .LT. 0) GO TO 11	ALL28170
12	Z=A2P/SA	ALL28180
C	SS=DCOS(Z*TRT)+LS*UO*DCOS(2.*Z*TRT)	ALL28190
C	SSI=DSIN(Z*TRT)+UO*DSIN(2.*Z*TRT)	ALL28200
C	SS=1.D0+LS*UO	ALL28210
C	SSI=0.D0	ALL28220
C	ARPI=A1*(SS+BR*SSI)*CDEXP(API*CK*TRT)+A2*(SS-BR*SSI)*CDEXP	ALL28230
C	1(ANO*API*CK*TRT)	ALL28240
	GO TO 13	ALL28250
11	Z=A2P/SA	ALL28260
C	SS=DCOS(Z*TRT)+LS*UO*DCOS(2.*Z*TRT)	ALL28270
C	SSI=DSIN(Z*TRT)+UO*DSIN(2.*Z*TRT)	ALL28280
C	SS=1.D0+LS*UO	ALL28290
C	SSI=0.D0	ALL28300
C	ARPI=A1*ANO*(BR*SS+SSI)*CDEXP(API*CK*TRT)+A2*(BR*SS-SSI)*CDEXP	ALL28310
C	1(ANO*API*CK*TRT)	ALL28320
13	ARPI=A1*CDEXP(API*CK*TRT)+A2*CDEXP(ANO*API*CK*TRT)	ALL28330
	ELOP=CDABS(ARPI)**2	ALL28340
	RETURN	ALL28350
	END	ALL28360
	SUBROUTINE SMAT(XU,X,YU,YUD,YV,YVD,ZK1,ZK2,YTH,I1,I2)	ALL28370
	IMPLICIT COMPLEX*16 (X-Z)	ALL28380
	DIMENSION XU(2,2),X(2,2)	ALL28390
	ZI=(0.D0,1.D0)	ALL28400
	XHA=(.5D0,0.D0)	ALL28410
	ZN1=(0.D0,-1.D0)	ALL28420
	ZGAN=CDEXP(ZN1*YTH)	ALL28430
	ZGA=CDEXP(ZI*YTH)	ALL28440
	ZIN=YU/YV	ALL28450
	ZID=(ZI*ZK1*YU+YUD)/(ZI*ZK2*YV+YVD)	ALL28460
	ZAL=ZIN+ZID	ALL28470
	ZBE=ZIN-ZID	ALL28480
	Z11=ZAL*ZGA	ALL28490
	Z12=ZBE*ZGA*I1	ALL28500

Z21=ZBE*ZGAN*I2	ALL28510
Z22=ZAL*ZGAN*I1*I2	ALL28520
X(1,1)=XHA*Z11*XU(1,1)+XHA*Z12*XU(2,1)	ALL28530
X(1,2)=XHA*Z11*XU(1,2)+XHA*Z12*XU(2,2)	ALL28540
X(2,1)=XHA*Z21*XU(1,1)+XHA*Z22*XU(2,1)	ALL28550
X(2,2)=XHA*Z21*XU(1,2)+XHA*Z22*XU(2,2)	ALL28560
1 CONTINUE	ALL28570
RETURN	ALL28580
END	ALL28590